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Voices of Inclusion: Understanding Student Insights on Diversity and Intercultural Competence in Higher Education

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Abstract: The present study seeks to explore the perceptions of ten students (N=10) studying at the School of Humanities and Social Sciences of the University of Patras regarding the necessity and the means of developing intercultural competence in academia. The qualitative methodology was followed and the purposive sampling procedure was applied. The students recognize as of major importance the necessity of inclusion and acceptance of diversity and cultivation of intercultural competence in the academic space, whereas they state that it is necessary for the academic community to strengthen mobility programs for both students and professors and to enrich the curricula with intercultural content.

Keywords: higher education, intercultural education and competence, inclusion, knowledge, skills, attitudes.

Introduction

In the last few years there has been a growing interest in developing intercultural competence in higher education, taking into account the contemporary context as it has been shaped by significant geopolitical and social changes, the almost simultaneous advent of the 4th and 5th Industrial Revolutions and the consequent demographic changes (Karanikola & Panagiotopoulos, 2023;

Rumbley & Sandström, 2019). In an attempt to conceptualize intercultural competence, we would note that there are various approaches and perspectives, as the term intercultural competence encompasses more and more different fields. One, however, widely accepted definition could be that intercultural competence constitutes a multidimensional construct that includes affective, cognitive and behavioral components (Chen, 2022; Mekheimer, 2019). The affective dimension refers to an individual's willingness to learn and appreciate different cultures. Then, the cognitive dimension involves the knowledge and understanding of various cultural norms, rules and practices., whereas the behavioral dimension "addresses the practical skills required to navigate intercultural interactions" (Ramstrand et al., 2024, p. 3).

Universities, in the context of the contemporary demand for extroversion, can play an important role in nurturing the knowledge, skills and attitudes that will help students to broaden their horizons and live at diversified societies by first enriching their curricula with relevant courses and enhancing the internationalization of both teachers and students. A review of the relevant literature demonstrates that interventions aimed at cultivating and promoting intercultural competence within the tertiary education context could be either pedagogical or immersion experiences (Zhang & Zhou, 2019). In particular, pedagogical interventions are applied in the teaching field and describe culture-based teaching materials, teaching methods and practices, integrated intercultural programmes and civic engagement experiences. In addition, immersion experiences typically refer to a brief or extended period of studying in a specific country, where students have the opportunity to reflect on their values, beliefs, biases and competences through their interaction in a new, different and dynamic cultural context (Ramstrand et al., 2024; Karanikola, 2025a; Karanikola & Panagiotopoulos, 2025; Leggett, 2020).

Research Aim and Research Questions

The current study attempts to investigate the perceptions of ten students (N=10) studying at the School of Humanities and Social Sciences of the University of Patras regarding the necessity and ways of developing intercultural competence in academia. In particular, participants were asked to answer the following open-ended questions. a) How would you define diversity in academia? b) How would you define intercultural competence? c) Do you think it is important to train students on diversity and intercultural issues? If so, why? If not, why? d) What intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes do you consider that you cultivate while attending university? e) Do you consider that the university you attend contributes to the cultivation of intercultural competence? If so, in what ways? If not, why not? f) Could you suggest other ways of fostering intercultural competence in academia?

Qualitative methodology, an important tool in the social sciences for more than a century (Adler & Clark, 2014), was adhered to, and the purposive sampling procedure was applied, as the aim was to explore future teachers' perceptions of the training they receive at undergraduate level on intercultural issues. The interview questionnaire consisted of two parts and was administered to the participants through a google form. The first part was to collect information about the demographic data of the participants (gender, age, foreign languages, year of study) and the second part consisted of six questions that essentially constitute the individual research questions. Thematic analysis was applied to process the qualitative data (Braun & Clark, 2006). The majority of the participants were women aged 20-22 years old who were in their third or fourth year of study and spoke at least one foreign language.

Research Results

When asked about how they define diversity, students focused on the association of diversity with inclusion, rights, respect, acceptance, freedom of expression and the specific characteristics of the individual that differentiate them from other members of the academic community. It is noteworthy that they also focus on language, religion, culture, elements that are essentially the main pillars of diversity (Karanikola & Balias, 2015). The following are indicative responses from the participants:

P1. "If I had to define diversity, it would be the acceptance of students and their inclusion in terms of their views and how they can freely express themselves within the university and through the work they are asked to produce."

P2. "Diversity is defined in relation to gender, age, sexual orientation, religion, political beliefs, language and culture."

P4. "When we refer to diversity, we mean all those different characteristics that individuals have between them...At the university there are students who come from different parts of Greece. This means that they may have a different language code (idiom). For example, children who come from Crete have a particular accent in their speech. There are also students from other countries. This may mean that in addition to the different language, they may also embrace a different religion. The only thing is that we have to respect each other's diversity."

P8. "Diversity, as we know, is individuals or small subsets of a larger group coexisting in a space with common purposes. Small subsets in academia are groups from other countries who are distinguished by the language they speak, their appearance, skin colour, age and habits. But diversity still exists even among students by year even by faculties and departments. Units of people who, because of their low self-esteem, move in isolation are also identified."

In a next step, students were asked to define intercultural competence, as this ability helps people with different linguistic and cultural capital to co-exist harmoniously and peacefully. According to their answers, intercultural competence is identified with the equal and fair coexistence of individuals and its core values are respect, flexibility, adaptability, empathy and sensitivity towards difference. Besides, intercultural sensitivity is a prerequisite for intercultural competence (Chen & Starosta, 2000). Indicatively:

P4. "Intercultural competence is the characteristic that allows a person not only to recognise but also to respect the different elements of the other. This means that the individual learns to deal sensitively and respectfully with the different elements that a person has at all levels, for example different religion, different language, different political and cultural beliefs or even different skin colour. If these are understood then individuals will coexist harmoniously with each other."

P9. "I think it has to do with knowledge, i.e. the amount one knows things about other cultures, i.e. culture, religion, customs and traditions..."

P10. "A person's ability to get along with people from different social groups."

The intercultural education of students is considered particularly important, as it can empower them with knowledge, skills and abilities to live in diverse and globalised societies, to accept their identities, to cooperate with international students and to study and work in other countries. However, a typical response is that of a student who considers that intercultural education for students is not necessary, as she believes that pathologies associated with discrimination, racism and prejudice are now largely a thing of the past (P7). Here are some more indicative answers:

P1. "I think it is very important that students receive intercultural education, because accepting diversity and coexisting in an intercultural environment can in itself make someone understand the value and weight of their identity, either by giving them the tools to support their own point of view and identity, or by making them able to listen and accept a different point of view or interpretation..."

P4. "Yes, it is important for students to be nurtured in intercultural education, because nowadays in our universities there are also students from other universities abroad. We may even be invited to go to study at a foreign university ourselves at some point. This automatically means that we will have to coexist with people who are different from us. So we should not be prejudiced against what is different in order to be able to work in harmony with people who are different from us."

P6. "Of course! We need to know, respect and accept difference as individuals and as a society. Yet there is a continuous tendency from civilized Christian (but not Islamic) countries for the most part to become more and more accommodating to issues of diversity and interculturality. This is of course legitimate but there should be limits."

P8. "Academia is an institution of knowledge and ideas where learners from different social levels, geographical regions, states, cities and villages with different cultures, customs and traditions come together to pursue a common purpose. It is necessary to develop empathy, respect, understanding, open-mindedness and peaceful coexistence. The overall benefits for the entire academic community will be many, and in the end, a solid basis for true partnerships, possibly genuine friendships based on universal human values will be created."

In terms of the intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes cultivated during their time at the university, students focus on developing critical thinking, empathy and openness as well as enriching their knowledge on issues of diversity, inclusion, human rights, identity, nationalism, pluralism, cultural theories, global issues, history and religion. In particular:

P10. "Especially during my studies at university, I came into contact with both teachers and students as well as with subjects that made me think critically about many issues of identity and diversity. I learnt what inclusion was because there was a lot of acceptance of difference and I saw that the emphasis was on one's opinion and positioning rather than one's background or the language in which one expressed it. Being at a younger age as well, I remember the impression that discussions about identity issues made on me, which I first came into contact with, and I think they had a particular impact on me then and have played a role in my way of thinking about difference and in defending it when it is met with unfair or unequal treatment."

P8. "Knowledge initially about our own culture, religion, values and beliefs we hold as individuals and society, knowledge of other countries' cultures, knowledge of world current events, knowledge of the environment, nature, climate change. Skills of empathy, acceptance, respect, understanding, mutual understanding, active listening, intercultural communication, conflict management. Attitudes of reflection on stereotypes, prejudices, questioning and evaluating ideas and beliefs, adopting a positive attitude towards difference."

P4. "Definitely recognizing and learning to respect diversity is something I've learned from a young age. What my university education helps me with is in learning it in practice. As the university is a place where people from different cultural backgrounds coexist."

P9. "Knowledge about world affairs, human rights, migration, understanding different cultures, stereotypes and prejudices. Also skills such as teamwork, critical thinking, adaptability, active

listening, conflict management and communication skills. Finally, attitudes such as self-awareness, empathy, respect for difference and cooperation."

It is noteworthy that the participating students state that the university contributes significantly to the cultivation of intercultural competence primarily through the courses offered at undergraduate and postgraduate level, the Erasmus mobility programmes, the learning of foreign languages and the respect shown towards the diversity of each individual. In particular:

P1. "The specific department I am currently attending, on the one hand because of the subject I have chosen, which is oriented towards the education of refugees and migrants, and on the other hand because of the temperament of the teachers who pay particular attention to intercultural issues, yes, it certainly contributes."

P2. "Yes, through the curriculum, the courses, the Erasmus programmes, the learning of foreign languages, the study of foreign texts, the coexistence with fellow students from different parts of Greece and with students with an immigrant/refugee background."

P5. "Yes! Through the curriculum and of course the high level of the teachers contributes to this."

P7. "Yes, the university contributes to the cultivation of intercultural competence through the coexistence of students of different origins, courses that promote cultural dialogue and activities with an international character."

In conclusion, the students acknowledge that intercultural competence can be further cultivated by enhancing discussion and intercultural dialogue, by increasing and financially supporting mobility programmes for both students and teachers, by creating networks and international action groups and by further encouraging participation in international conferences. In particular:

P8. "I believe that writings can come from different cultural backgrounds and students should be encouraged to express themselves freely based on their own identity and perspective without a sense of criticism or right and wrong."

P2. "To strengthen student and teacher exchange programmes between countries, to further strengthen volunteering and social actions..."

P5. "Difficult question! One could say more seminars and trainings, more Erasmus students, introduction of courses on interculturalism..."

P6. "Paying for travel to conferences abroad for students."

Conclusions

The present research allows us to draw some findings representative of the perceptions of the participating students. First, students recognize the necessity of being educated at the undergraduate level on diversity management issues through the development of intercultural competence consisting of knowledge, skills and attitudes. According to Chen and Starosta (2000), intercultural competence consists of intercultural awareness, intercultural sensitivity and intercultural adroitness. Intercultural knowledge refers to an individual's ability to understand the similarities and differences between cultures. Intercultural sensitivity refers to an individual's emotional desire to learn about, appreciate and accept cultural differences, and its key elements are self-esteem, self-control, empathy, openness, non-judgement and social relaxation. Intercultural competence is the behavioral dimension of intercultural competence and refers to one's ability to achieve communication goals in

one's interaction with people from other cultures. In this respect, the Intercultural Competence Model of Schnabel et al. (2015) advocates sensitivity to the verbal and non-verbal aspects of intercultural communication, the deliberate search for information about other countries and different cultures, socialization and establishing/maintaining contacts with people from other cultures, mediation between parties to achieve maximum benefit for all, and intense and continuous reflection on one's cultural characteristics.

However, the academic community needs to be further empowered both at the pedagogical level and at the level of immersion experiences (Karanikola, 2025a). In particular, it needs to incorporate intercultural competence at both the micro (lesson plans, syllabi, teaching methodologies, learning materials) and macro-level (language policies, curriculum structures, staff and faculty appropriate training, staff and students' recruitment policies) (Strotmann & Kunschak, 2022; Karanikola, 2025a, b). In light of this, Han and Zhu (2022) also state that universities should engage in activities and experiences, such as overseas exchanges, joint degrees, and sustainable programmes. In addition, promoting intercultural competence translates in facilitating interaction between national and international students, giving students a voice probably through digital communication platforms, and seeking agreement of all agents regarding democratic and intercultural values (Karanikola, 2025b).

Concluding, research findings reveal that the main objective of education is to not only educate the mind, but to develop more complex types of intellectual development necessary for effective intercultural citizenship (Leggett, 2020). Finally, we could not but mention the limitations of this research, which are inescapable mainly due to the restricted number of participants, the limited geographical area in which it took place and the research design itself.

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